

Synthesis of gadolinium doped nickel zinc ferrite nanoparticles for biosensor application

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Abstract

The promising ferrite nanoparticles are now-a-days widely used in the field of biological and medical science due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, superparamagnetic nature and easily tuned by external magnetic field. These magnetic nanoparticles can develop linkages with minute antibiotic-resistant bacteria present in contaminated waste water, for fighting nosocomial infections and in medical field used for MRI, hyperthermia treatment and biosensor applications. Nickel zinc ferrite nanoparticles with composition of $(\text{NiZn})_{0.5}\text{Gd}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (where $x=0.1, 0.2, 0.3$) were synthesized by economic and facile chemical co-precipitation process. The structure, lattice parameters and crystalline size of these prepared nano particles are derived from their X-ray diffraction patterns to correlate their dependence on gadolinium ions concentration. These random shaped nanoparticles have faceted morphology with sharp edges and vertices as seen from HRTEM micrographs. The average particle size is found to vary from 15 - 25 nm. FTIR transmission spectra of these NiZn ferrite nanoparticles are recorded in $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ by using sample in a KBr pellet form. The strong transmittance peaks at about 540 cm^{-1} and 480 cm^{-1} are the characteristic stretching modes arising from the vibrations of FeO_4 tetrahedron and FeO_6 octahedron present in spinel gadolinium ions doped NiZn ferrite nanoparticles. In addition to these modes, the transmission peaks pertaining to the surfactant oleic acid carbonyl ($-\text{COOH}$), methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$), methylene ($-\text{CH}_2$), ethene ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$) and C-C functional groups are obtained as weak, medium and strong intensity peaks in $\sim 1760-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The appearance of these peaks confirms the capping of nanoparticles through weak hydrogen bonding. The magnetic measurements are also carried at room temperature by using VSM technique. The saturation magnetization of these samples is found to decrease with increase in gadolinium concentration.

Keywords: Co precipitation, Magnetic, FTIR.